

Supplementary Table 3: Performance of datasets with the best solution obtained by *BayesNet Naives (NB)*.

Experiment	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	F1-score	Specificity
<i>AD vs. HC</i>	0.9528	0.9659	0.9659	0.9659	0.9231
<i>FTD vs. HC</i>	0.9925	0.9286	0.9630	0.9455	0.8462
<i>AD vs. FTD</i>	0.9882	1	0.9773	0.9885	1
<i>PPA variants</i>	0.8676	0.95	0.8261	0.8837	0.9778